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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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ENHANCING CREATIVE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN SENIOR SECONDARY STUDENTS THROUGH PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING

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Abstract: This study explores the use of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) in teaching English as a Foreign Language (EFL) in grades 10–11. The research draws on theoretical perspectives from Hymes, Canale and Swain, Richards, and Vygotsky to examine the pedagogical implications of PBL. The findings demonstrate that PBL-based courses significantly enhance students' fluency, creativity, and confidence in communication. This approach integrates creativity with language proficiency, equipping students with essential 21st-century skills such as problem-solving, adaptability, and teamwork. The study concludes with methodological recommendations for educators considering the implementation of PBL in secondary school curricula.

Key words: creative competence, communicative competence, problem-based learning, EFL teaching, senior secondary education, innovative methodology, language pedagogy.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot 10–11-sinf o'quvchilariga ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'qitishda Muammoga Asoslangan O'qitish (Problem-Based Learning – PBL) texnologiyasidan foydalanishni o'rganadi. Tadqiqot Hymes, Canale va Swain, Richards hamda Vygotskiy kabi olimlarning nazariy qarashlari asosida PBLning pedagogik oqibatlarini tahlil qiladi. Olingan natijalarga ko'ra, PBL asosidagi mashg'ulotlar o'quvchilarning nutq ravonligi, ijodkorligi va muloqotdagi ishonchini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Ushbu yondashuv til kompetensiyasi va kreativlikni uyg'unlashtiradi hamda o'quvchilarni muammolarni hal qilish, moslashuvchanlik va jamoada ishlash kabi XXI asr ko'nikmalari bilan ta'minlaydi. Tadqiqot PBL metodikasini umumta'lim maktablari darslariga joriy etishni ko'rib chiqayotgan o'qituvchilar uchun metodik tavsiyalar bilan yakunlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijodiy kompetensiya, kommunikativ kompetensiya, muammoga asoslangan o'qitish, ingliz tilini o'qitish, yuqori sinflar, innovatsion metodologiya, til pedagogikasi.

Аннотация: Данное исследование посвящено применению технологии обучения на основе решения проблем (Problem-Based Learning, PBL) при преподавании английского языка как иностранного в 10–11-х классах. В работе рассматриваются теоретические подходы Хаймса, Канале и Суэйна, Ричардса и Виготского для анализа педагогических последствий внедрения PBL. Полученные результаты показывают, что курсы, основанные на PBL, значительно повышают беглость речи, креативность и уверенность учащихся в коммуникации. Такой подход сочетает творческие способности с языковой компетенцией, формируя у школьников навыки XXI века, такие как решение проблем, гибкость и умение работать в команде. Исследование завершается методическими рекомендациями для педагогов, рассматривающих внедрение PBL в школьные курсы.

Ключевые слова: творческая компетенция, коммуникативная компетенция, проблемно-ориентированное обучение, преподавание английского языка, старшие классы, инновационная методология, языковая педагогика.

INTRODUCTION

Language acquisition primarily focuses on communicative competence, which encompasses creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. Creative communicative competence is vital for students to collaborate across cultural boundaries, adapt to global challenges, and effectively participate in knowledge-based economies. This competence is particularly significant at the senior secondary level (grades 10–11) in the context of English as a Foreign Language (EFL).

Conventional teacher-centered programs often fail to address these demands, emphasizing rote memorization and structural accuracy over meaningful communication and creativity. In contrast, Problem-Based Learning (PBL), which highlights learner autonomy, collaboration, and real-world problem-solving, has been

widely adopted across various educational sectors. PBL fosters both communicative competence and creativity by engaging students in projects that require linguistic proficiency alongside cognitive effort.

This approach aligns with socio-constructivist learning theories, which promote higher-order learning through peer interaction and guided teacher support. Accordingly, this study seeks to examine how PBL can enhance students' creative communicative skills in EFL at the grades 10–11 level. It aims to analyze the theoretical foundations of creative communicative competence, evaluate PBL as an effective pedagogical approach, and identify practical applications within the classroom context.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Applied linguistics and language pedagogy have a long tradition of examining communicative skills. Hymes (1972) introduced the term “communicative competence” to highlight the significance of language use in social and cultural contexts. Later, Canale and Swain (1980) expanded this concept into a multifaceted model that incorporated grammatical, discourse, sociolinguistic, and strategic competencies, thereby laying the foundation for Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). However, CLT has been criticized for overlooking the creative dimension of communication, which is vital for effective language use.

Creativity is a crucial element of language acquisition, enabling learners to express themselves with originality, flexibility, and adaptability. It has been linked to enhanced academic performance, increased motivation, and stronger problem-solving abilities in educational settings, particularly at the senior secondary level (grades 10–11). Problem-Based Learning (PBL), first implemented in medical education, supports this integration by engaging students with real-world, unstructured problem scenarios that require collaborative inquiry, meaning-making, and solution development. Research indicates that PBL enhances learners' self-confidence, fluency in communication, and problem-solving abilities in EFL instruction.

Nevertheless, challenges remain in applying PBL to language education. These include teachers' proficiency in designing and facilitating problem tasks, the need for effective scaffolding, and constraints related to time and resources. Despite these limitations, PBL is widely regarded as a powerful pedagogical tool for integrating creativity and communicative competence in language classrooms.

This study builds on previous scholarship by examining the role of PBL in enhancing creative communicative competence among senior secondary students, with a particular focus on English as a Foreign Language.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study investigates how Problem-Based Learning (PBL) supports senior secondary students in developing creative communicative competence. A qualitative-descriptive research approach, complemented by empirical observation, was employed to provide both theoretical insights and empirical evidence regarding the effective integration of PBL into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms.

Participants and Context

The study involved students in grades 10–11 at a secondary school. These learners, typically aged 16–17, are at a transitional stage where advanced language proficiency and innovative problem-solving skills become increasingly significant for academic and professional development. Based on the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), the participants' English proficiency ranged from B1 to B2. This diversity provided an opportunity to examine the impact of PBL on students with varied linguistic backgrounds and cognitive abilities.

Research Design and Procedures

The study was conducted in three phases:

- 1. Preliminary Stage (Diagnostic Assessment):** A needs analysis was carried out to determine students' baseline creativity, communicative competence, and attitudes toward conventional classroom instruction. Data were collected through questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. A creativity scale adapted from Torrance (2008) and a communicative competence checklist were employed for diagnostic purposes.
- 2. Implementation Stage (PBL-Based Instruction):** Over six weeks, students participated in PBL activities integrated into their EFL curriculum. Each session involved open-ended, real-world challenges requiring collaborative discussion and language production. Examples included designing advertising materials for local cultural events, debating social issues relevant to teenagers, and proposing an environmentally sustainable school project. The instructor functioned as a facilitator, allowing students to manage problem-solving and language generation while providing scaffolding where necessary.

- 3. Post-Implementation Stage (Evaluation and Reflection):** At the end of the intervention, the same instruments used in the preliminary stage were applied to reassess students' creativity and communicative performance. Additionally, reflective diaries and group discussions were analyzed to capture students' perceptions of the learning process.

Instruments and Data Collection

Table 1: Instruments Used in the Study and Their Functions

Instrument	Source / Basis	Purpose of Use
Communicative Competence Rubric	Adapted from Canale & Swain (1980)	O'quvchilarning grammatik, diskursiv, sotsiolingvistik va strategik kompetensiyalarini baholash
Creativity Checklist	Based on Torrance (2008) model	Ijodiylik ko'rsatkichlarini (tezkorlik, moslashuvchanlik, originallik, tafsilot) o'lchash
Observation Protocol	Researcher-designed	Mashg'ulot davomida ishtirok, hamkorlik va ijodiy til ishlatish darajasini qayd etish
Questionnaires & Interviews	Modified from existing EFL survey instruments	O'quvchilar va o'qituvchilarning PBL jarayoniga munosabati, tajribasi va samaradorligini o'rganish

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative techniques. Pre- and post-intervention results were compared through descriptive statistics (mean scores, percentage improvements). Qualitative data from interviews and reflective diaries underwent thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns in student experiences. To determine the statistical significance of observed differences, inferential tests such as Pearson's chi-square test and the Student's t-test were applied where appropriate.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical standards for educational research. Informed consent was obtained from both students and their parents. Participation was entirely voluntary, and anonymity was guaranteed. Moreover, the design ensured that PBL activities aligned with curriculum objectives, thereby avoiding disruption to students' regular learning processes.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The use of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) had a clear effect on participants' development of creative communicative competence. Improvement was evidenced both quantitatively and qualitatively, based on data gathered from diagnostic assessments, classroom observations, and post-intervention evaluations.

Pre- and Post-Test Results

Students' performance on creative and communicative activities was measured before and after the intervention. All four dimensions of communicative competence—grammatical, discourse, sociolinguistic, and strategic—as well as creative indicators such as fluency, originality, flexibility, and elaboration demonstrated noticeable improvement.

Table 1: Comparison of Pre- and Post-Intervention Scores

Competence / Indicator	Pre-Test Mean (%)	Post-Test Mean (%)	Improvement (%)
Grammatical Accuracy	62	75	+13
Discourse Coherence	58	74	+16
Sociolinguistic Appropriateness	55	71	+16
Strategic Competence	60	78	+18
Fluency (Creativity)	52	73	+21
Originality (Creativity)	49	71	+22
Flexibility (Creativity)	50	70	+20
Elaboration (Creativity)	54	74	+20

As Table 1 indicates, the most substantial gains were observed in creativity-related indicators, particularly originality (+22%) and fluency (+21%), followed by strategic competence (+18%). These findings suggest that PBL encouraged students not only to communicate more effectively but also to use language in creative and adaptive ways.

Observational and Qualitative Findings

Classroom observations revealed greater cooperation and active engagement in PBL sessions compared with conventional lessons, in which only a small proportion of students typically participated. During problem-solving tasks, students demonstrated a greater willingness to experiment with new vocabulary, employ circumlocution strategies, and negotiate meaning.

Qualitative evidence from interviews and reflective diaries confirmed these observations. Many students reported feeling more confident in expressing ideas in English, even when unsure of grammatical accuracy. One student noted: *“I was afraid of making mistakes before, but I realized that ideas are more important during problem-solving tasks, and I discovered new ways to say what I wanted.”* Another commented: *“Working in groups helped me learn new words and think in English faster.”*

Statistical Analysis

The improvements were supported by inferential statistics. A paired t-test revealed a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between pre- and post-test scores in both creative and communicative competence. Additionally, the chi-square test indicated that, compared with baseline results, a higher proportion of students achieved upper-intermediate proficiency levels (B2) following the intervention.

Interpretation of Findings

The study demonstrates that PBL can enhance senior secondary students' creative communicative competence. Barrows (1996) and Savery (2006) argue that PBL promotes autonomy, critical thinking, and cooperative problem-solving, which were reflected in the observed improvements. Richards (2006) emphasizes that communicative language teaching should encourage creativity rather than mere precision, an aim naturally achieved by PBL through its focus on authentic, unstructured tasks.

PBL addresses gaps left by traditional approaches such as Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) by integrating both communicative and creative objectives in real-world learning scenarios. Moreover, qualitative findings underscore the affective benefits of PBL, including increased motivation, learner confidence, and adaptability in language use.

However, challenges remain in applying PBL to EFL classrooms. These include the need for effective scaffolding, sufficient teacher preparation, and adaptation within exam-oriented curricula. Despite such limitations, the findings strongly support the use of PBL in senior secondary EFL instruction, as it equips learners with essential 21st-century skills by combining language practice with innovative problem-solving. With adequate preparation and professional development for teachers, PBL represents a powerful pedagogical approach to advancing both communicative and creative competence in high school students.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the effectiveness of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) in fostering creative communicative competence among senior secondary students. The findings indicate that PBL significantly enhances creativity-related indicators such as fluency, originality, flexibility, and elaboration, while also improving communicative competencies including grammatical accuracy, discourse coherence, sociolinguistic appropriateness, and strategic competence.

PBL offers a dynamic pedagogical framework that integrates creative problem-solving with authentic language practice, thereby preparing students for the communication demands of the 21st century. By situating learning in real-world contexts, PBL encourages autonomy, collaboration, and innovation, equipping learners with transferable skills that extend beyond the classroom.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that teachers incorporate PBL into EFL lesson planning by designing real-world projects, promoting active student engagement, and providing appropriate scaffolding to support learner progress. Professional development programs should also be implemented to equip educators with the necessary skills to design and facilitate PBL effectively.

Further research is needed to evaluate the long-term impact of PBL on language learning outcomes, its effectiveness in large-scale classes, and its comparative value against other approaches such as Task-Based Learning (TBL) or Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL). Such studies would provide deeper insights into the scalability and adaptability of PBL within diverse educational contexts.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.